

Influence of Five 'E's Instructional Model on the Proficiency in Understanding the Concept of Cell Division among Secondary School Students in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the Effect of 5E's instructional Model on Performance in Concept of Cell Division among Secondary School Students in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of 14, 567 Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2021/2022 academic session in the six educational zones. Total sample of five hundred and twelve (512) Senior Secondary School class two students were used for the study. Purposive sampling technique was employed and instrument used for collection of data is Cell Division performance test (CDPT). The instrument was validated by experts in the department of Biological sciences Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto and experienced secondary school biology teachers and reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. Two objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of mean and Standard Deviation. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance using Analysis of Covariance the three hypotheses were rejected. The findings of the study shows that students taught cell division using 5E's instructional model outperformed better than those taught using conventional method. The findings also revealed that female students taught using 5's instructional model performed better than their male counterpart. The study recommended among others that teachers should be trained on the use of 5E's instructional strategy in teaching cell division concepts.

Keyword: 5E's Instructional Model, Academic Performance and Cell Division

Introduction

Education is a fundamental human right and the structural key to sustainable development, peace and stability of a nation. In Nigeria, education is perceived as an instrument for achieving national objectives. Science and technology have been playing a major role towards the growth and development of any given nation. Biology as one of science subjects most especially in the secondary schools is key and paramount in science endeavor. According to the National Policy on Education (NPE 2013), the objective of biology at the senior school level is to develop interest in the subject, acquire interest in science, technology and mathematics, to apply scientific skills, to meet societal needs. Education is an instrument per excellence for the achievement of national development. One major key of Nigeria vision 20-20 is to provide students with vibrant and modern science education system that will provide meaningful learning (NPE, 2013). This opens opportunity for students to achieve maximum potentials and provide the nation with adequate and competent man power needs. Biology is a unique branch of natural sciences, however, like other natural sciences; it is concerned with the search for in-depth understanding of natural phenomena and events. Several studies such as that of Nelvin (2017), Mohammed (2016), Ibrahim (2015), Jesulowo (2019), were carried out to improve teaching and learning of biology.

The shift to inquiry-based pedagogical practices in the classroom may necessitate a transition from textbook-dependency as the main resource of science information to a more hands-on approach, where students are central to the learning episodes. Recent research findings have shown that an inquiry-based approach is beneficial to students and that even young children can learn through inquiry processes (Santrock, 2011). Despite the investment in science education, to meet up with the present challenge of the 21st century, Students' performance at SSCE had still been recorded very low in biology when compared with the number of enrolment of students over the years. (Okoli, 2015 Mohammed & Sakiyo 2017). The Chief Examiners report on Senior Secondary School Students achievement in biology revealed that, the subject had both the highest

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enrolment relative to other science subjects and recorded poor achievement in the senior school certificate examination (SSCE). Adeduran, (2001), Ajajun and Tayo (2007), observed that Nigerian Educational system is still confronted with poor academic performance. Aderogba (2006), is of the view that the academic performance of students in biology includes observation and measurable behavior of students at any point during a course, either in theory or practical. The academic performance consist of the students' scores at any particular time obtain from a teacher made test. In other words, academic performance can be placed with observed behavior or expectation of achieving a specific statement of objective. Researches have been conducted on factors which could affect the academic performance of students in sciences in an attempt to find out why students performances have been low (Unuroh,2004; Okebukola, 2005; Olanrewaju, 2009). Such studies considered students competence, instructional strategies and difficulties encountered in problem solving and learning outcomes.

Sokoto State Government however, are still implementing all necessary initiatives that will help to boost the morale of students in attaining educational success of students and teachers as a result of lack of tangible improvement in academic performance (Benevino, 2015). Secondary school students' performance in Biology have made Sokoto States government to embark on many measures to ensure effective teaching and learning. One of such measures was the free Science extra academic coaching for SS classes sponsored by the then executive governor of Sokoto State in 2016 (Aliyu Foundation, 2016). According to the Ministry of Education report on performance trend Sokoto State was among the States that was recorded to have 23.15% of 5 credits points and above (WAEC, 2019). This is still an indication of the decrease in the credit level of academic performance in school results. To improve student's engagement performance in classroom and to facilitates the use of more effective instructional model that will enable the students to learn more, retain more and apply what is learned. Several versions of learning models have been proposed ranging from 3E's to 7E's.

5E's instructional model is a consequence of constructivist learning theory which basically asserts that students construct their own knowledge. It is this situation that motivated the researcher to investigate the impact of 5E's instructional model on performance, in cell division among Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State Nigeria. There is a need to engage in significant and appealing activities. As a result, the 5E instructional model may be appropriate in this regard. The 5E's instructional model is a type of constructivist approach that can be used in biology to increase the quality of teaching and learning. Bybee (2002) asserted that the use of 5Es instructional model can helps students redefine, organize, examine and change the ideas they already have through interacting with their peers and environment. According to Bybee (2002), the 5E's instructional model is a technology enriched model which enable the learners to develop 21st century skills as well as the teachers to teach specific concept in biology and to provide good reform-based instruction. The cycle consists of cognitive stages of learning that begins with letter E engage, explore, explain, elaborate, and evaluate. Science teachers and curriculum developers may integrate or apply the model at several levels. The model can be the organizing pattern of a sequence of daily lessons, individual units, or yearly plans. Each phase of the 5E Instructional Learning Cycle is described as follows;

The engage phase enable the teacher as an instructor to open a lesson with an activity or questions meant to engage students, snag their interest, and offer the opportunity for them to share what they already know. This phase is aims to assess student prior knowledge and or identify possible misconceptions. This student-centered phase should be a motivational period that can create a desire to learn more about the upcoming concept. Students may brainstorm an opening question or ask themselves: "What do I already know about this concept?" Discrepant events, demonstrations, questioning, or graphic organizers may be included to create interest or generate curiosity. Students are to brainstorm and record what they Know, want to know, and (eventually) have Learned about the concept.

The Exploration phase following an engagement phase, promotes a mental focus on the concept, the exploration phase provides the students with a common, concrete learning experience. This phase is also student-centered and incorporates active exploration. Students are encouraged to apply process skills, such as observing, questioning, investigating, testing predictions, hypothesizing, and communicating, with other peers. This phase of the learning model tends to incorporate the main inquiry-based activity or experience, which encourages students to develop skills and concepts. The teacher's role is one of facilitator or consultant. In addition, students are encouraged to work in a cooperative learning environment without direct instruction from the teacher. This phase is also unique because the students are given a "hands-on" experience before any formal explanation of terms, definitions, or concepts are discussed or explained by the teacher.

The Explanation phase is a "minds-on" phase following the exploration phase, and this is more teacher-directed and guided by the students' prior experience during the exploration phase. The explanation phase enables students to describe their understanding and pose questions about the concepts they have been exploring. It is likely that new questions will be generated. The explanation phase is an essential, minds-on part of the 5E lesson. Before the teacher attempts to provide an explanation, the students must first have the opportunity to express their own explanations and ideas. Thus, the initial part of the explanation

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phase is a time for the teacher to serve as a facilitator and ask the students to describe and discuss their exploration learning experiences. After the students have had the opportunity to share their own explanations, the teacher introduces scientific and technical information in a direct manner. This phase includes clarification of student misconceptions that may have emerged during the engagement or exploration phases. Formal definitions, notes, and labels are provided. The teacher may also decide to integrate video, computer software programs, power point presentations or other visual aides to help with student understanding. The students should then be able to clearly explain the important concepts to the teacher and to their peers.

Elaboration phase activities of the learning cycle should encourage students to apply their new understanding of concepts, while reinforcing new skills. Students are encouraged to check for understanding with their peers, or to design new experiments or models based on the new skills or concepts they have acquired. The goal of this phase is to help develop deeper and broader understandings of the concepts. Students may conduct additional investigations, develop products, share information and ideas, or apply their knowledge and skills to other disciplines. This is a great opportunity to integrate science with other content areas. Elaboration activities may also integrate technology, such as web-based research or Web Quests.

Evaluation phase is the assessment inquiry-based setting which is very different from traditional science lessons. Both formal and informal assessment approaches are appropriate, and should be included. For instance, the use of non-traditional forms of assessment, such as portfolios, performance-based assessment, concept maps, physical models, or journal logs may serve as significant evidence of student learning. During an inquiry-based lesson, assessment should be viewed as an ongoing process, with teachers making observations of their students as they apply new concepts and skills and looking for evidence that the students have changed or modified their thinking. Students may also have the opportunity to conduct self-assessment or peer-assessment

Several studies have been reviewed on the efficacy of 5E's instructional model on academic performance such as Nelvin (2017) who conducted a meta-analysis study to evaluate the effect of the 5E learning model on academic achievement, and scientific process skills. The result of the study shows that 5E learning model had an effect on the students' academic achievement, attitude towards science and science process skills. To determine the effects of learning cycle as an instructional strategy on biology students' achievement, Ajaja and Eravwoke (2012) included two instructional groups (experimental and control groups). The samples of the study were six senior secondary schools with 112 science students, and 12 biology teachers. The instruments used for this study were: teacher's questionnaire on knowledge and use of learning cycle (KULC); on Biology Achievement Test (BAT). The data collected were analyzed with simple percentage, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and student t-test statistics. The major findings of the study revealed that, only 30.43% and 26.31% of biology teachers have the knowledge that learning cycle as an instructional method; all the biology teachers sampled have never used learning cycle as an instructional method; learning cycle had a significant effect on students' achievement in biology. Students taught with learning cycle significantly achieved better in biology Post-test than those taught with lecture method; the post-test scores of students in the 5E's learning cycle group increased over the period of experience; It was concluded that the method seems to be an appropriate instructional model that could be used to solve the problems of science teaching and learning since it facilitates learning and retention

The impact of using 5E's Instructional Model on academic achievement in biology and retention of learning among fifth grade students was investigated by Mohammed (2016). Experiment group were 30 student, and control group were 29 students. Pre and post tests were used to determine the difference in the two groups. Experiment group was taught using the 5E's instructional model. T-test was used to check the significant difference between experiment and control group after experiment. It is explored that both the groups were equal regarding their achievement scores in pre-test before the experiment, but after experiment both were different in their achievement test scores in favor of experiment group. It is concluded that this significant performance of experiment group may be due to use of 5E's instructional model. The study recommended that modern and practical instructional techniques using constructivist approaches would enhance the need to improve students learning at the elementary schools. Appropriate training for teachers to use (5E's) instructional model to teach mathematics would enhance the active learning. The findings of Odagboyi (2015) who examined the effect of gender on the achievement of students in biology using the 5E's method. Results shows that there was a significant difference between the mean scores in favor of the female. This implies that the females gained more from the 5E's instructional; method compared with the males.

The investigation of the effects of 5E learning model on creativity, performance and retention in ecology among Secondary school Students in Zaria Education Zone was done by Jesulowo (2019). The result of the study shows that the experimental group had significantly higher scores than conventional lecture method group. The study recommended that teachers should be encourage to use 5E instructional model to teach ecology concepts in secondary schools.

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The investigation of gender differences in biology academic achievements levels using 5Es instructional model among secondary school students in Kenya. Was carried out by Busola (2012) who found out that girls performed better than boys.

The impact of 5E’s teaching cycle on attitude retention and performance in genetics among Pre-NCE students with varied ability conducted by Ibrahim (2015), revealed that Pre-NCE students exposed to 5E’s teaching cycle showed better performance when compared to those not expose to it. The study also recommended that the, teaching of biology especially genetics should be conducted using 5Es’ teaching cycle as it makes students learn meaningfully, enhance better performance and retention of knowledge and develop positive attitude towards the subject. The investigation of gender differences among biology students in a cooperative class was carried out by Mathew and Young (2007) who conducted a study on 149 students, not randomly selected in biology. They found there was a significant difference in the performance females with regard to the males. The mean Scores of the females were higher than that of males.

The fluctuating trend in Senior Secondary School Students Performance in external examination in Biology has become a source of worry to researchers in science education. Many factors have been identified to be responsible for this menace. This include the use of inappropriate and non-effective teaching methodology, students lack of interest, existence of abstract concepts, student’s misconception of science, improper use of instructional materials, large class size, lack of well-trained teachers, constant use of lecture method and over loaded curriculum. Table 1 below depicts the fluctuating trends of student’s performance in Biology.

Table 1: Trends of Students’ Performance in May \ June Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination in Biology, 2016 to 2022.

Year	Total Students that Sat	No of Students with C6 and above	% Percentage Pass	% Parentage Fail
2016	1646150	587040	35.66	64.34
2017	1648363	736970	44.70	55.30
2018	1365384	685970	50.02	49.98
2019	1471151	583486	39.66	60.34
2020	1572396	758424	48.23	51.77
2021	1522321	647212	23.51	76.49
2022	1628356	623873	26.10	73.90

Source: West African Examination Council (WAEC 2022) National Head Office Yaba, Lagos

Table 1 shows the fluctuating trend in Nigerian Secondary Student Performance in West African Senior School Certificate Examination in Biology, between 2016 to 2020. In 2016, only 35.66% of students passed out of the total enrolment of 1,646,150. The trend increased in 2017 and 2018 to 44.70% and 50.02%. While 39.66% and 48.23% in 2019 and 2020 respectively. There was a decrease in students’ performance in 2019, which recorded 39.66% credit pass. The performance is not satisfactory acceptable because 64.34%, 55.3%, 60.34% and 51.77% of the students failed which is still large. The concern of every well-meaning stakeholder in education is therefore expected to be geared towards improving the performance of students in Biology with a view to reducing the percentage failure and upgrading the percentage pass. The WAEC chief examiners Reports consistently claim that there is the need for students to improve in understanding and application of cell division, genetics concepts and principles, laws and theories. Despite the emphasis and importance of various teaching methods and facilities in science process, there is still a high rate of failure in biology. This is as a result of the poor presentation of Biology by teachers as abstract and uninteresting subject. The findings of previous studies Ibrahim 2015, Mohammed 2016, Ajaja and Erawoke 2012 and Jesulowo 2019 Shows that students have difficulties, misconceptions and confusion in cell division. This makes students hate the topic and the situation lead to poor performance of students in biology especially at the Senior Secondary School Level. The prevailing teaching method does not allow active students participation in biology lessons. Students only memorize and regurgitate facts and concepts. However, some teachers are not aware of the significant suitable method due to inadequate knowledge or perhaps low professional training. Teachers are not competent enough to adapt hard but suitable method.

Therefore, 5E’s instructional model is the hard but suitable 21st century constructivist- oriented teaching approach which improves the teaching of science by actively engaging learners in authentic practical investigation that enable them to develop more realistic ideas about scientific study as well as offer a more motivating and learner-centered environment. Education Researchers found out that the use of 5E’s instructional approach could assist teachers and learners, promote positive change in students attitude. Towards learning, increase student’s willingness to learn and foster performance (Opara, 2011).

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The problem of this study therefore is about effects of 5E's Instructional Model on Students Academic Performance in cell division among senior secondary schools' students in Sokoto State Nigeria. How can the use of 5E's instructional Model improve academic performance in Sokoto State?

Objectives of the study

1. Investigate the differences in academic performance between secondary school students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model and those exposed to cooperative method State the objective in clear, unambiguous and should reflect thrust of the study.
2. Investigate the differences in academic performance between secondary school male and female students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to be tested in the study

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference between academic performance of secondary school students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model and those exposed to conventional method.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference between academic performance of secondary school male and female students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model.

Methodology

The study adopted quasi experimental research design. the subjects were grouped into two groups experimental and control group. The experimental group were exposed to 5E's instructional model while the control group were exposed to conventional method. Both groups were subjected to pre-test and post-test. The population comprises of 14, 567 SSII students drawn from the six educational zone in Sokoto State. The total schools in the six educational zone is 118. One school was selected randomly in each zone and two intact classes were used in each school, comprising of 123 males and 389 females. Purposive sampling technique was employed to select a total of 512 students for the study. The instrument used for data collection was Cell Division Performance (CDPT) which contains 30 relevant items on cell division drawn from past WAEC and NECO questions. The researcher considers questions from WAEC and NECO appropriate because they have already been standardized. The instrument was validated by experts from the Department of Science and Vocational Education and the Department of Biological Sciences of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto. The reliability of the instrument (BPT) was established using Split-half method during the pilot study at the pretest stage. Two public Secondary Schools that were not part of the sample of this study was selected for this exercise. The experimental group was taught cell division using 5E's while the control group was taught cell division using cooperative method. The scores of the instruments were computed and split into odd and even numbers. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to correlate the scores and obtained the index of 0.61. This is the reliability of the half of the instrument. The index was beefed up using Prophecy formula to obtain the reliability index of 0.85 for the whole instrument. This is considered high enough for administration. All the research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation while inferential statistics was used to test the null hypotheses on performance. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was most appropriate for the research since the subjects are not randomized and the data contain pre-test and post-test.

Results

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between academic performance of secondary school students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model and those exposed to conventional method.

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Table 2: Summary of Tests Between-Subjects Effects of 5E's Instructional Model and Cooperative Method on Performance of Students in Cell Division

Source of Variance	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	η^2
Corrected Model	7756.82	2	3878.413	347.721	.000	.577
Intercept	2939.050	1	2939.050	263.502	.000	.341
Pre-test scores	166.722	1	166.722	14.948	.000	.029
Strategy	4087.215	1	4087.215	366.442	.000	.419
Error	5677.282	509	11.154			
Total	214531.000	512				
Corrected Total	13434.107	511				

Table 2 revealed the result of a one-way between-group analysis of covariance conducted to determine the difference in the performance of students taught cell division using 5E's instructional model with those taught using cooperative method. The independent variable was instructional method (5E's & Cooperative), and the dependent variable consisted of post-test scores on Biology Performance Test (BPT) administered after the intervention was completed. Biology Performance Test (BPT) administered before intervention were used as the covariate in this analysis. After the effect of pre-test scores (covariate) has been partial out, the result revealed that there was a significant difference between the post-test scores of experimental (5E's) and control (cooperative method) groups thought cell division using 5E's instructional model and those thought using cooperative method. ($F(1, 509) = 366.422, p = .000, p < .05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .419$). Since p value is less than .05, the stated null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, this result implies that there was a significant difference in the performance of students taught cell division using 5E's instructional model with those taught using cooperative method. Experimental treatments were able to account for 41.9% of the observed variance noticed in the dependent variable.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between academic performance of secondary school male and female students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model.

Table 3: Summary of Tests Between-Subjects Effects of Gender on Performance of Students taught Cell Division using 5E's Instructional Model

Source of Variance	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	η^2
Corrected Model	2679.774	2	1339.887	162.300	.000	.540
Intercept	2621.810	1	2621.810	317.578	.000	.535
Pre-test scores	101.924	1	101.924	12.346	.001	.043
Gender	2572.963	1	2572.963	311.661	.000	.530
Error	2278.555	279	8.256			
Total	156905.000	281				
Corrected Total	4958.330	280				

η^2 = Eta Squared

Table 3 revealed the result of a one-way between-group analysis of covariance conducted to determine the gender difference in the performance of students taught cell division using 5E's instructional model. The independent variable was gender (male & female), and the dependent variable consisted of post-test scores on Biology Performance Test (BPT) administered after the intervention was completed. Biology Performance Test (BPT) administered before intervention were used as the covariate in this analysis. After the effect of pre-test scores (covariate) has been partial out, the result revealed that there was a significant difference between the post-test scores of male and female students taught using 5E's instructional model ($F(1, 276) = 311.661, p = .000, p < .05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .530$). Since p-value is less than .05, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This result implies that there was a significant difference between academic performance of secondary school male and female students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model. Gender was able to account for 53.0% of the observed variance noticed in the dependent variable.

Discussion of Finding

The paper investigated the Effect of 5E's instructional Model on Performance in Concept Cell Division among Secondary School Students in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Table 1 shows Tests Between-Subjects Effects of 5E's Instructional Model and Cooperative Method on Performance of Students in Cell Division ($F(1, 509) = 366.422, p = .000, p < .05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .419$). Since p value is less than .05, the stated null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, this result implies there is significant difference between academic performance of secondary school students taught concept cell division using 5E's instructional model and those exposed to conventional method. The study agrees with the findings of Ajaja and Eravwoke (2012). They determine the effects of 5E's learning cycle as an instructional strategy on biology and students' achievement. The result shows that 5E's learning model had a significance effects on the student's academic achievements in biology. The post-test scores of students in the 5E's learning cycle group increased over the period of experience.

The result of the study of Jesulowo (2019) which investigated the effects of 5E learning model on creativity, performance and retention in ecology among Secondary school Students in Zaria Education Zone shows that the experimental group had significantly higher scores than conventional lecture method group. This result is unanimous with the findings of this presents study. Similarly, this study also agrees with the findings of Ibrahim (2015), on the impact of 5E's teaching cycle on attitude retention and performance in genetics among Pre-NCE students with varied ability revealed that Pre-NCE students exposed to 5E's teaching cycle has better performance when compared to those not expose to it and therefore, encourage the teaching of biology with the use of 5E's instructional model as it makes students learn meaningfully, and enhance better performance.

Table 2 shows Tests Between-Subjects Effects of Gender on Performance of Students taught Cell Division using 5E's Instructional Model the findings shows that there was a significant difference between the post-test scores of male and female students taught using 5E's instructional model ($F(1, 276) = 311.661, p = .000, p < .05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .530$). Since p -value is less than .05, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Female students have a significant higher mean score than their male counterparts when taught using 5E's instructional model. Gender was able to account for 53.0% of the observed variance noticed in the dependent variable. The findings of this study contradict the results of the investigation conducted by Ibrahim (2015) And Jesulowo (2019) who investigated the effect of gender and the academic performance of students taught ecology using 5E learning model. The result of the study shows that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of both male and female students taught Ecology using 5E-Learning model. Both male and female students have relatively the same level of increased academic performance.

The present study agrees with the result of Busola (2012) who investigated gender differences in Biology achievements levels among secondary school students in Kenya. The findings revealed that, girls performed better than boys. The findings of the present study also agree with the result of Odagboyi (2015) who examined the effect of gender on the achievement of students in biology using the 5E's instructional method. Results shows that there was a significant difference between the mean scores in favor of the female. This implies that the females gained more from the use of 5E's instructional method compared with the males.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of this study, it was concluded that there was a significant difference in the performance of students taught cell division using 5E's Instructional model with those taught using cooperative method. It was also discovered that there was a significant difference in the performance of male and female students taught cell division using 5E's instructional model. 5E's instructional model is not gender friendly as it is very effective for the enhancement of female students' performance in cell division concepts. Female students have a significant higher mean score than their male counterparts when taught using 5E's instructional model. When the effects of cooperative method on performance of gender was investigated, it was found that there was a significant difference between male and female students taught using cooperative method.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were based on the findings of this study

1. It is recommended that teachers should be trained in the use of 5E's as instructional strategy in teaching cell division concept because the study shows that it is more effective than cooperative method.
2. The use of 5E's Instructional Model should be encouraged among male and female students through careful supervision.
3. It is recommended that in cooperative learning strategy, integration of groups should be encouraged.

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